

International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management (IJMFM)

ISSN: 2348 –3954 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 –2546 (Print)

Email us: editor@arseam.com

<http://www.arseam.com/>

Download Full Paper:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-2-issue-11-dec-2014>

**Impact
Factor:
0.98**

A STUDY ON DERIVATIVES: AN AVENUE FOR INVESTMENT IN INDIA

Dr. Shailendra Singh Bhadouria

Associate Professor & Head (Commerce)
IGNTU, Amarkantak M.P.

Abstract

The benefits of derivatives are threefold: (i) risk management, (ii) price discovery, and (iii) enhancement of liquidity. Given the seemingly important benefits, why are derivatives, and especially credit derivatives, viewed so negatively in the current financial crisis? The problem is not with the derivatives as an instrument, but with (i) the way they were traded and cleared, and (ii) how they were used by some financial institutions to increase their exposure to certain asset classes. In India, the emergence and growth of derivatives market is relatively a recent phenomenon. Since its inception in June 2000, derivatives market has exhibited exponential growth both in terms of volume and number of contract traded. The market turnover has grown from Rs.2365 Cr. in 2000-2001 to Rs.16807782.22 Cr. in 2012-13. Within a short span of twelve years, derivatives trading in India has surpassed cash segment in terms of turnover and number of traded contracts. The passed study encompasses in its scope, history, concept, definition, types, features, regulation, market, trend, growth, Future prospects and challenges of derivatives in India and status of Indian derivatives market vis-à-vis global derivative market.

Key words: Derivatives, Exponential Growth, Risk Management, Price Discovery, SENSEX

INTRODUCTION

Companies are exposed to different hazards in their normal day to day operations and when borrowing the capital. For some of the hazards, management can achieve security from an insurance corporation. For instance, management can assure a plant against devastation through fire by getting a fire insurance plan from a casualty and property insurance corporation. But Capital market products which are available to management to secure against different hazards are not insurable through an insurance corporation. These hazards include hazards connected with changes in the price of an input, a reduction in price of a commodity the company sells, an increase in the cost of borrowing investments, and an unfavourable movement of exchange rate (Jana, 2010). The tools that can be applied to present these securities are identified as derivative tools, so called because they obtain their importance from whatever the agreement is based on. These tools comprise futures agreements, forward agreements, alternative agreements, swap contracts, and floor and cap contracts“Derivatives are financial contracts whose value is derived from some underlying asset. These assets can include equities and equity indices, bonds, loans, interest rates, exchange rates, commodities, residential and commercial mortgages, and even

catastrophes like earthquakes and hurricanes". The contracts come in many forms, but the more common ones include options, forwards/futures and swaps.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The paper examines risk exposures through derivatives in India. Specifically, objectives of the study include:

- 1) To examine the meaning of derivatives;
- 2) To highlight the underlying assets in a derivative contract;
- 3) To identify classes of derivatives and derivative market participants;
- 4) To explore commodity derivatives and financial derivatives;
- 5) To identify factors that contribute to the rapid growth of derivative markets; and
- 6) To outline the potential benefits of derivatives for Indian economy.

METHODOLOGY

The study is done mainly by collecting and analysing secondary data. The main sources of these data are website and publications of the CBN. In addition, relevant literature is reviewed to obtain knowledge working procedure of the study. Essentially, the adoption of secondary data for the study is reasonable as there is little data on derivatives in India because the nation's derivative market is relatively new and passive.

Derivative securities: some basic concepts

The Oxford dictionary defines a derivative as something derived or obtained from another, coming from a source; not original. In the field of financial economics, a derivative security is generally referred to a financial contract whose value is derived from the value of an underlying asset or simply underlying. There are a wide range of financial assets that have been used as underlying, including equities or equity index, fixed-income instruments, foreign currencies, commodities, credit events and even other derivative securities. Depending on the types of underlying, the values of the derivative contracts can be derived from the corresponding equity prices, interest rates, exchange rates, commodity prices and the probabilities of certain credit events.

Definition of financial derivatives

A derivative is a financial product which has been derived from another financial product or commodity. D.G. Gardener defined the derivatives as "A derivative is a financial product which has been derived from market for another product." The securities contracts (Regulation) Act 1956 defines "derivative" as under section 2(ac). As per this "Derivative" includes (a) "a security derived from a debt instrument, share, loan whether secured or unsecured, risk instrument or contract for differences or any other form of security." (b) "a contract which derived its value from the price, or index of prices at underlying securities." The above definition conveys that the derivatives are financial products. Derivative is derived from another financial instrument/ contract called the underlying. A derivative derives its value from underlying assets. Accounting standard SFAS133 defines a derivative as "a derivative instrument is a financial derivative or other contracts will all three of the following characteristics: (i) It has (1) one or more underlying, and (2) one or more notional amount or payments provisions or both. Those terms determine the amount of the settlement or settlements. (ii) It requires no initial net investment or an initial net investment that is smaller than would be required for other types of contract that would be expected to have a similar response to changes in market factors. (iii) Its terms require or permit net settlement. It can be readily settled net by a means outside the contract or it provides for delivery of an asset that puts the recipients in a position not substantially different from net settlement.

From the aforementioned, derivatives refer to securities or to contracts that derive from another whose value depends on another contract or assets. As such the financial derivatives are financial instrument whose prices or values are derived from the prices of other underlying financial instruments or financial assets. The underlying instruments may be an equity share, stock, bond, debenture, treasury bill, foreign

currency or even another derivative asset hence, financial derivatives are financial instruments whose prices are derived from the prices of other financial instruments

Underlying asset in a derivatives contract

As defined above, its value is entirely derived from the value of the underlying asset. The underlying asset can be securities, commodities, bullion, currency, livestock or anything else. In other way the underlying asset may assume many forms:

- (i) Commodities including grain, coffee beans, orange juice;
- (ii) Precious metals like gold & silver;
- (iii) Foreign exchange rates or currencies;
- (iv) Bonds of different types, including medium to long term negotiable debt, securities issued by governments, companies etc;
- (v) Shares and share warrants of companies traded on recognized stock exchanges and stock index;
- (vi) Short term securities such as T-bills;
- (vii) Over the counter (OTC) money market products such as loans or deposits.

The Major Players of Derivatives Market.

There are three major players in the financial derivatives trading:

1. Hedgers: Hedgers are traders who use derivatives to reduce the risk that they face from potential movements in a market variable and they want to avoid exposure to adverse movements in the price of an asset. Majority of the participants in derivatives market belongs to this category.

2. Speculators: Speculators are traders who buy/sell the assets only to sell/buy them back profitably at a later point in time. They want to assume risk. They use derivatives to bet on the future direction of the price of an asset and take a position in order to make a quick profit. They can increase both the potential gains and potential losses by usage of derivatives in a speculative venture.

3. Arbitrageurs: Arbitrageurs are traders who simultaneously buy and sell the same (or different, but related) assets in an effort to profit from unrealistic price differentials. They attempt to make profits by locking in a riskless trading by simultaneously entering into transaction in two or more markets. They try to earn riskless profit from discrepancies between futures and spot prices and among different futures prices.

Uses of financial derivatives

Derivatives are supposed to provide some services and these services are used by investors. Some of the uses and applications of financial derivatives can be enumerated as following:

- 1. Management of risk:** One of the most important services provided by the derivatives is to control, avoid, shift and manage efficiently different types of risk through various strategies like hedging, arbitrating, spreading etc. Derivatives assist the holders to shift or modify suitable the risk characteristics of the portfolios. These are specifically useful in highly volatile financial conditions like erratic trading, highly flexible interest rates, volatile exchange rates and monetary chaos.
- 2. Measurement of Market:** Derivatives serve as the barometers of the future trends in price which result in the discovery of new prices both on the spot and future markets. They help in disseminating different information regarding the future markets trading of various commodities and securities to the society which enable to discover or form suitable or correct or true equilibrium price in the markets. As a result, they assist in appropriate and superior allocation of resources in the society.
- 3. Efficiency in trading:** Financial derivatives allow for free trading of risk components and that leads to improving market efficiency. Traders can use a position in one or more financial

derivatives as a substitute for a position in underlying instruments. In many instances, traders find financial derivatives to be a more attractive instrument than the underlying security. This is mainly because of the greater amount of liquidity in the market offered by derivatives as well as the lower transaction costs associated with trading a financial derivative as compared to the costs of trading the underlying instruments in cash market.

- 4. Speculation and arbitrage:** Derivatives can be used to acquire risk, rather than to hedge against risk. Thus, some individuals and institutions will enter into a derivative contract to speculate on the value of the underlying asset, betting that the party seeking insurance will be wrong about the future value of the underlying asset. Speculators look to buy an asset in the future at a low price according to a derivative contract when the future market price is high, or to sell an asset in the future at a high price according to derivative contract when the future market price is low. Individual and institutions may also look for arbitrage opportunities, as when the current buying price of an asset falls below the price specified in a futures contract to sell the asset.
- 5. Price discovery:** The important application of financial derivatives is the price discovery which means revealing information about future cash market prices through the future market. Derivative markets provide a mechanism by which diverse and scattered opinions of future are collected into one readily discernible number which provides a consensus of knowledgeable thinking.
- 6. Price stabilization function:** Derivative market helps to keep a stabilizing influences on spot prices by reducing the short term fluctuations. In other words, derivatives reduces both peak and depths and lends to price stabilization effect in the cash market for underlying asset.
- 7. Gearing of value:** Special care and attention about financial derivatives provide leverage (or gearing), such that a small movement in the underlying value can cause a large difference in the value of the derivative.
- 8. Develop the complete markets :** It is observed that derivative trading develop the market towards “complete markets” complete market concept refers to that situation where no particular investors be better of than others, or patterns of returns of all additional securities are spanned by the already existing securities in it, or there is no further scope of additional security
- 9. Encourage competition :** The derivatives trading encourage the competitive trading in the market, different risk taking preference at market operators like speculators, hedgers, traders, arbitrageurs etc. resulting in increase in trading volume in the country. They also attract young investors, professionals and other experts who will act as catalysts to the growth of financial market.
- 10. Liquidity and reduce transaction cost :** As we see that in derivatives trading no immediate full amount of the transaction is required since most of them are based on margin trading. As a result, large number of traders, speculators, arbitrageurs operates in such markets. So, derivatives trading enhance liquidity and reduce transaction cost in the markets of underlying assets.
- 11. Hedging:** Hedge or mitigate risk in the underlying, by entering into a derivative contract whose value moves in the opposite direction to their underlying position and cancels part or all of it out. Hedging also occurs when an individual or institution buys an asset and sells it using a future contract. They have access to the asset for a specified amount of time, and can then sell it in the future at a specified price according to the futures contract of course; this allows them the benefit of holding the asset.
- 12. Other uses :** The other uses of derivatives are observed from the derivatives trading in the market that the derivatives have smoothen out price fluctuations, squeeze the price spread, integrate price structure at different points of time and remove gluts and shortage in the markets. The derivatives also assist the investors, traders and managers of large pools of funds to device such

strategies so that they may make proper asset allocation increase their yields and achieve other investment goals.

Types and classification of derivatives

There are many ways in which the derivatives can be categorized based on the markets where they trade; based on the underlying asset and based on the product feather etc. some ways of classification are following:

(1) On the basis of linear and non-linear: On the basis of this classification the financial derivatives can be classified into two big class namely linear and non-linear derivatives:

(a) Linear derivatives: Those derivatives whose values depend linearly on the underlying are value is called linear derivatives. They are following:

(i) Forwards (ii) Futures (iii) Swaps

(b) Non-linear derivatives: Those derivatives whose value is a non-linear function of the underlying are called non-linear derivatives. They are following:

(i) Options (ii) Convertibles (iii) Equity linked bonds (iv) Reinsurances

(2) On the basis of financial and non-financial: On the basis of this classification the derivatives can be classified into two category namely financial derivatives and non-financial derivatives.

(a) Financial derivatives: Those derivatives which are of financial nature are called financial derivatives. They are following:

(i) Forwards (ii) Futures (iii) Options (iv) Swaps

The above financial derivatives may be creditderivatives, forex, currency fixed-income, interest, insider trading and exchange traded.

(b) Non-financial derivatives: Those derivatives which are not of financial nature are called non-financial derivatives. They are following:

(i) Commodities (ii) Metals (iii) Weather (iv) Others

(3) On the basis of market where they trade : On the basis of this classification, the derivatives can be classified into three categories namely; OTC traded derivatives, exchange-traded derivative and common derivative.

(a) Over-the-counter (OTC) traded derivative : These derivative contracts are traded (and privately negotiated) directly between two parties, without going through an exchange or other intermediary. The OTC derivative market is the largest market for derivatives and largely unregulated with respect to disclosure of information between parties. They are following: (i) Swaps (ii) Forward rate agreements (iii) Exotic options (iv) Other exotic derivative

(b) Exchange traded derivative: Those derivatives instrument that are traded via specialized derivatives exchange of other exchange. A derivatives exchange is a market where individual trade standardized contracts that have been defined by the exchange. A derivative exchange act as an intermediary to all related transactions and takes initial margin from both sides of the trade to act as a guarantee. They may be followings:

(i) Futures (ii) Options (iii) Interest rate (iv) Index product (v) Convertible (vi) Warrants

(c) Common derivative : These derivatives are common in nature/trading and classification. They are following:

(i) Forwards (ii) Futures (iii) Options (iv) Binary options (v) Warrant (vi) Swaps

The various types of financial derivatives based on their different properties like, plain. Simple or straight forward, composite, joint or hybrid, synthetic, leveraged, mildly leveraged, customized or OTC traded, standardized or organized exchange traded, regulated and unregulated.

Regulation of Derivatives trading in India

The regulatory frame work in India is based on L.C. Gupta Committee report and J.R. Varma Committee report. It is mostly consistent with the international organization of securities commission (IUSCO). The L.C. Gupta Committee report provides a perspective on division of regulatory responsibility between the exchange and SEBI. It recommends that SEBI's role should be restricted to approving rules, bye laws and regulations of a derivatives exchange as also to approving the proposed derivatives contracts before commencement of their trading. It emphasises the supervisory and advisory role of SEBI. It also suggests establishment of a separate clearing corporation.

Derivatives Market in India

In India, there are two major markets namely National Stock Exchange (NSE) and Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) along with other Exchanges of India are the market for derivatives. Here we may discuss the performance of derivatives products in Indian market.

Derivative products traded at BSE

The BSE started derivatives trading on June 9, 2000 when it launched "Equity derivatives (Index futures-sensex) first time. It was followed by launching various products which are shown in table no.2. They are index options, stock options, single stock futures, weekly opotions, stocks for: Satyam, SBI, Reliance Industries, Tata Steel, Chhota (Mini) Sensex, Currency futures, US dollar-rupee future and BRICSMART indices derivatives. The table No.2 summarily specifies the derivative products and their date of introduction at BSE.

Table 1: Derivative products of BSE

S No	Introduction date	Derivative Products
1	9th June 2000	Equity derivatives (Index futures – SENSEX)
2	1st June 2001	Index options launched (Index options Sensex)
3	9th July 2001	Stock options launched (Stock option on 109 stocks)
4	9th Nov. 2002	Stock futures launched (Stock futures on 109 Stocks)
5	13 SEP 2004	Weekly options on 4 Stocks
6	1st Jan. 2008	Chhota (mini) sensex
7	NA	Futures options on sectoral indices (namely BSE TECK, BSE FMCG, BSE metal, BSE Banke bse oil & gas)
8	1st Oct. 2008	Currency derivative introduced (currency futures on US Dollar)
9	30th March 2012	Launched BRICSMART

Derivative products traded at NSE

The NSE started derivatives trading on June 12, 2000 when it launched "Index Futures S & P CNX Nifty" first time. It was followed by launching various derivative product which are shown in table no.3. They are index options, stock options, stock future, interest rate, future CNX IT future and options, Bank Nifty futures and options, CNX Nifty Junior futures and options, CNX100 futures and options, Nifty Mid Cap-50 future and options, Mini index futures and options, Long term options. Currency futures on USD-

rupee, Defty future and options, interest rate futures, SKP CNX Nifty futures on CME, European style stock options, currency options on USD INR, 91 days GOI T.B. futures, and derivative an global indices and infrastructures indices. The table no.3 presents a description of the types of derivative product traded atNSE and their data of introduction at NSE.

Table 2: Derivative products of NSE

S NO	Introduction date	Derivative Products
1	12th June 2000	Index futures – S&P CNX Nifty
2	4th June 2001	Index Options – S&P CNX Nifty
3	2nd July 2001	Stock options – on 233 stocks
4	9th Nov. 2001	Stock futures on 233 stocks
5	23rd June 2003	INTERST RATE FUTURES-TBILLS&10
6	29th Aug. 2003	CNX IT futures & options
7	13th June 2005	Bank Nifty futures & options
8	1st June 2007	CNX Nifty Junior Futures & Options
9	1st June 2007	CNX 100 futures & options
10	5th Oct. 2007	Nifty midcap – 50 futures & options
11	1st Jan. 2008	Mini index futures & options – S&P CNX Nifty Index

Source: Compiled from NSE website

Growth of Indian derivatives market

The NSE and BSE are two major Indian markets have shown a remarkable growth both in terms of volumes and numbers of traded contracts. Introduction of derivatives trading in 2000, in Indian markets was the starting of equity derivative market which has registered on explosive growth and is expected to continue the same in the years to come. NSE alone accounts 99% of the derivatives trading in Indian markets. Introduction of derivatives has been well received by stock market players. Derivatives trading gained popularity after its introduction in very short time.

If we compare the business growth of NSE and BSE in terms of number of contracts traded and volumes in all product categories with the help of table no.4, table no.5 and table no.12 which shows the NSE traded 636132957 total contracts whose total turnover is Rs.16807782.22 cr in the year 2012-13 in futures and options segment while in currency segment in 483212156 total contracts have traded whose total turnover is Rs.2655474.26 cr in same year. In case of BSE the total numbers of contracts traded are 150068157 whose total turnover is Rs.3884370.96 Cr in the year 2012-13 for all segments. In the above case we can say that the performance of BSE is not encouraging both in terms of volumes and numbers of contracts traded in all product categories. The table no.4, table no.5 and table no.12 summarily specifies the updated figures since 2003-04 to 2012-13 about number of contracts traded and total volumes in all segments

Table 3: Business growth of NSE in FO Segment

Year	Total No. of Contracts	Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Average Daily Turnover
2012-13	636132957	16807782.22	120055.59
2011-12	1205045464	31349731.74	125902.54
2010-11	1034212062	29248221.09	115150.48
2009-10	679293922	17663664.57	72392.07
2008-09	657390497	11010482.20	45310.63
2007-08	425013200	13090477.75	52153.30
2006-07	216883573	7356242	29543
2005-06	157619271	4824174	19220
2004-05	77017185	2546982	10107
2003-04	56886776	2130610	8388

Source: Compiled from NSE website

Table 4: Business growth of NSE in CD Segment

Year	Total No. of Contracts	Total Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Average Daily Turnover
2012-13	483212156	2655474.26	19383.02
2011-12	973344132	4674989.91	19479.12
2010-11	749602075	3449787.72	13854.57
2009-10	378606983	1782608.04	7427.53
2008-09	32672768	162272.43	1167.43

Source: Compiled from NSE website

As per above table it is seen that because of increasing in the number of contracts there is increases in total turnover and also increases in average daily turnover so we can say derivatives shows a rapid growth in credit segments

Table5: Different kinds of derivatives in INDIA has made their position

Year	Index Futures Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Stock Futures Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Index Option Notional Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Stock Option Notional Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Total Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Average Daily Turnover (Rs. Cr.)
2012-13	1522594.88	2146022.55	12228169.28	910995.66	16807782.22	120055.59
2011-12	3577998.41	4074670.73	22720031.64	977031.13	31349731.74	125902.54
2010-11	4356754.43	5495766.70	18365365.76	1030344.21	29248221.09	115150.48
2009-10	3934388.67	5195246.64	8027964.20	506065.18	17663664.57	72392.07
2008-09	3570111.40	3479642.12	3731501.84	229226.81	11010482.20	45310.63
2007-08	3820667.27	7548563.23	1362110.88	359136.55	13090477.75	52153.30
2006-07	2539574	3830967	791906	193795	7356242	29543
2005-06	1513755	2791697	338469	180253	4824174	19220
2004-05	772147	1484056	121943	168836	2546982	10107
2003-04	554446	1305939	52816	217207	2130610	8388

From the above table it is clear that the different kinds of derivatives in INDIA has made their strong position and help in the economic development of the country

Table 6: Number of Contract traded at NSE in CD

Year	Currency Futures No. of Contracts	Currency Options No. of Contracts	Total No. of Contracts
2012-13	354111488	129100668	483212156
2011-12	701371974	271972158	973344132
2010-11	712181928	37420147	749602075
2009-10	378606983	-	378606983
2008-09	32672768	-	32672768

Source: Compiled from NSE website

From the above table also position of derivatives is declining in the previous year but overall position is strong.

Table 7: Average daily transaction at NSE in FO

Year	Total No. of Contracts	Total Turnover (Rs. Cr)	Average Daily Turnover (Rs.)
2012-13	636132957	16807782.22	120055.59
2011-12	1205045464	31349731.74	125902.54
2010-11	1034212062	29248221.09	115150.48
2009-10	679293922	17663664.57	72392.07
2008-09	657390497	11010482.20	45310.63

2007-08	425013200	13090477.75	52153.30
2006-07	216883573	7356242	29543
2005-06	157619271	4824174	19220
2004-05	2546982	2546982	10107
2003-04	56886776	2130610	8388

Source: Compiled from NSE website

From the table we get the increasing trend of the daily transactions throughout these years and it will show a good position of derivatives in the Indian market.

Table 8: Average daily transaction at NSE in CD

Year	Total No. of Contracts	Total Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Average Daily Turnover (Rs. Cr.)
2012-13	483212156	2655474.26	19383.02
2011-12	973344132	4674989.91	19479.12
2010-11	749602075	3449787.72	13854.57
2009-10	378606983	1782608.04	7427.53
2008-09	32672768	162272.43	1167.43

Source: Compiled from NSE website

Table 9: Business growth at BSE in all Segments

Year	Total Contracts	Total Turnover (Rs Cr)	Average Daily Turnover (Rs Cr)	Trading Days
2012-13	1500681	5730828.34	30828.34	126
2011-12	32222825	808475.99	3246.89	249
2010-11	5623	154.33	0.61	255
2009-10	9028	234.06	1.04	224
2008-09	496502	11774.83	48.46	243
2007-08	7453371	242308.41	965.37	251
2006-07	1781220	59006.62	259.94	227
2005-06	203	8.78	.14	61
2004-05	531719	16112.32	77.09	209
2003-04	143224	5021.81	81	62

Source: Compiled from BSE website.

Table 10: Product wise turnover of futures at BSE

Year	Index Futures Turnover	Equity Futures Turnover (Rs.)	Trading Days
2012-13	104188.65	125.98	126
2011-12	178448.83	10215.70	249
2010-11	154.08	0.00	255
2009-10	96.00	0.30	224
2008-09	11757.22	8.49	243
2007-08	234660.16	7609.24	251
2006-07	55490.86	3515.50	227
2005-06	5.00	0.49	61
2004-05	13599.66	212.85	209

SOURCE: COMPLIED FROM BSE WEBSITE

From the above table different kinds of derivatives shows remarkable performance so we can say it is one of the good financial instrument.

TABLE-11: PRODUCT WISE TURNOVER OF OPTION ATBSE

Year	Index option Call Turnover (Rs Cr)	Index option Put Turnover (Rs Cr)	Equity option Call Turnover (Rs Cr)	Equity option Put Turnover (Rs Cr)	Trading Days
2012-13	1967091.23	1812758.37	45.13	162.26	126
2011-12	200089.57	418252.79	1277.27	191.82	249
2010-11	0.00	0.25	0.00	0.00	255
2009-10	137.76	0.00	0.00	0.00	224
2008-09	6.11	3.01	0.00	0.00	243
2007-08	31.00	7.66	0.21	0.14	251
2006-07	0.06	0.00	0.16	0.04	227
2005-06	3.20	0.00	0.09	0.00	61
2004-05	1470.61	826.62	2.08	0.50	209
2003-04	0.00	0.00	139.07	119.77	62

Source : Compiled from BSE website.

Conclusions:

In terms of the growth of derivatives markets, and the variety of derivatives users, the Indian market has equaled or exceeded many other regional markets.¹³ while the growth is being spearheaded mainly by retail investors, private sector institutions and large corporations, smaller companies and state-owned institutions are gradually getting into the act. Foreign brokers such as JP Morgan Chase are boosting their presence in India in reaction to the growth in derivatives. The variety of derivatives instruments available for trading is also expanding. There remain major areas of concern for Indian derivatives users. Large gaps exist in the range of derivatives products that are traded actively. In equity derivatives, NSE figures show that almost 90% of activity is due to stock futures or index futures, whereas trading in options is limited to a few stocks, partly because they are settled in cash and not the underlying stocks. Exchange-traded derivatives based on interest rates and currencies are virtually absent. Liquidity and transparency are important properties of any developed market. Liquid markets require market makers who are willing to buy and sell, and be patient while doing so. In India, market making is primarily the province of Indian private and foreign banks, with public sector banks lagging in this area (Fitch Ratings, 2004). A lack of market liquidity may be responsible for inadequate trading in some markets. Transparency is achieved partly through financial disclosure. Financial statements currently provide misleading information on institutions' use of derivatives. Further, there is no consistent method of accounting for gains and losses from derivatives trading. Thus, a proper framework to account for derivatives needs to be developed. Further regulatory reform will help the markets grow faster. For example, Indian commodity derivatives have great growth potential but government policies have resulted in the underlying spot/physical market being fragmented (e.g. due to lack of free movement of commodities and differential taxation within India). Similarly, credit derivatives, the fastest growing segment of the market globally, are absent in India and require regulatory action if they are to develop. As Indian derivatives markets grow more sophisticated, greater investor awareness will become essential. NSE has programmes to inform and educate brokers, dealers, traders, and market personnel. In addition, institutions will need to devote more resources to develop the business processes and technology necessary for derivatives trading

So we can say derivatives for the Indian markets are boon not the curse.

References:

- [1]. B. Brahmaiah and Rao P. Subba, "Financial futures and option", 1st ed., Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi, 1998, PP.25-147.
- [2]. D. Vasant, "The Indian financial system and development", 4th ed., Himalaya Publishing House, New Delhi, 2012, PP.398-412, 645-677.
- [3]. M. Gurusamy, and J. Sachin, "Financial derivatives", 1st ed., Ramesh Book Depot, New Delhi, 2009-10, PP.1.01-5.10.
- [4]. M. Ranganatham and R. Madhumathi, "Security analysis and portfolio management", 1st ed., Pearson education, New Delhi, 2011, PP.723-730.
- [5]. R.P. Rustagi, "Investment analysis and portfolio management", 1st ed., Sultan Chand & Sons, New Delhi, 2007, PP.459-596.
- [6]. S. Kevin, "Security analysis and portfolio management", 6th Pr., PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2009, PP.232-270.
- [7]. S.S.S. Kumar, "Financial derivatives", 2nd Pr., PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2008, PP.1-27, 57-306.
- [8]. S.L. Gupta, "Financial derivatives", 6th Pr., PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2009, PP.3-551.
- [9]. V.A. Avadhani, "Security analysis and Portfolio MANAGEMENT"
- [10]. V. Gangadhar, G. Ramesh Babu, "Investment management", 1st rep., Anmol Publication Pvt. Ltd., 2006, PP.437-465.
- [11]. John C. Hull, "Futures and options markets", 2nd ed., PHI Learning Private Ltd., New Delhi, 2009, PP.1-169.
- [12]. 'Trading statistics of derivatives segment at BSE', available at: www.bseindia.com (accessed on October 20, 2012)